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Circular economy model in Electronics and High-Tech Sector- A study of sustainable business management in India

Dr. Jayasree Nambiar**Asst. Professor,**

Balaji College of Arts, Commerce and Science, Pune-33

e-mail id: jayapradeepnambiar@gmail.com

Mobile No: 9921089518

Abstract:

In India, the initiative towards industrial development started since 1991. The increase in income, growth of industrial sector and change in consumption pattern of the people cumulated in to increase in demand for industrial products. Affiliation towards foreign sector also led to increase in imports and large-scale production of electronic and consumer durable goods. Majority of rural and urban households owns these goods and also change it as and when the new fashion and trend arrives in the market. In this context there is a need to study the introduction of circular economy model in order to reduce solid waste and unnecessary increase in landfills. The new term circular electronics focus on consumer durable- electronics and high-tech sector. This research study is based on secondary data confined to the discussion on the alarming increase in non-degradable waste and the importance of introduction of purely circular economy business management model to support the highly increasing electronic goods manufacturing sector- Use, Reuse, Refurbish.

Keywords: Circular economy, manufacturing sector, Business models, consumer durable, land fills

Introduction-

Electronics sector is the world's fastest-growing waste generating stream, amounting to an estimated 57.4 million tonnes in 2021. The amount of waste from electrical and electronic sector generated globally increased from 44.7 Mt in 2016 to 53.6 Mt in 2019, and is anticipated to reach 74.7 Mt by 2030. Out of this, less than 20% of global e-waste is formally collected and recycled. The rest is ends up in waste dumps where they are burned, dismantled, or melted without proper security checking. This leads to severe environmental pollution and health hazards. The fastest growing sector in India is Electronics and High-Tech manufacturing sector. The expected growth rate of this sector is ~\$400bn by 2025. The basic growth drivers are increase in demand for consumer electronics products like smartphones, tablets and laptops and changing life style of the people. In this context the need of sustainable business management model gains coin. The thought process in this direction concluded with the new terminologies

like Circular Economy, Industrial Ecology and short supply chains etc. leading to transformation of existing method of production and consumption, particularly on regional scales. The circular economy concept is opposed to the linear model of resource consumption based on the " take, make, dispose " triptych typical of our industrial societies. The circular economy is based on the tag line "eliminate waste" by turning goods which are at the end of their life in to new goods or resources for another consumer. A per FICCI study, approximately half-a-trillion dollars' worth of economic value that can be unlocked through Circular Economy business models in India by 2030 (10). The study of circular economy system is more pertinent to the consumption of Electrical and Electronic Equipment (EEE). On an average, the total weight (excluding photovoltaic panels) of global EEE consumption increases annually by 2.5 million metric tons (Mt). In 2019, the world generated a striking 53.6 Mt of e-waste, an average of 7.3 kg per capita. This research study is going to focus on how to implement circular economy business model in Indian EEE sector to achieve more sustainable business management.

Research Methodology

This research is based on secondary data published in journals, government websites etc. Various research papers published in google scholar, web of science also referred while doing this research. This research is more of descriptive in nature.

Objectives

1. To study the importance of introducing circular economy model in Electronics and High-Tech Sector.
2. To review the process of introduction of circular business management model in Indian electronic sector.
3. To understand the experience of other economies already introduced CE model.

Conceptualization

Over the past 20 years, industrial objects became services and systems of touch points, digital interfaces, and more than that, with digitalization introduced the Internet of Things and machine learning systems. As a result of these our cities grew bigger, our networks of production and trading more articulate and our societies became more multicultural. The recent consumer expenditure survey (32) reveals that there is a considerable increase in the living standard of the people in India. Manufacturing sector survey report (14) is another proof to increase in production of Consumer electronics goods. People are exposed to new life style and with modern amenities of life. People are exposed to foreign markets due to Globalization. Consumption pattern of the potential customers are changing continuously. The impact of all these developments is increase in solid waste and landfills. The introduction of circular economy model and strict implementation of this by assigning the task to the producers and creating awareness to the people to use the products optimally to avoid waste can reduce landfills and reduce the pressure on land.

Research Gap

The researcher had gone through 20 research papers related to this topic. But a study linking the changing consumption pattern of Indians and the growing importance to consumer electronics and possible impact on sustainable development process has not been available. So, in this research paper the researcher is reviewing various aspects like the status of production of consumer durables, consumer expenditure survey report, measures taken by NITI Ayog and data on solid waste generation in India. There is a significant gap between e-waste generation and collection for recycling, necessitates proper assessment to make resource efficiency effective in India. This research paper is intended to through light on the expected impact on land due to increase in landfills and the need to follow the circular business model.

Review of Literature

To achieve consistent economic growth, poverty alleviation, hunger elimination, human development, and environmental improvement in India, new transformative and effective solutions are needed to be implemented rather than incremental improvements. Proper system to be implemented to avoid the concern on greenhouse gases (GHGs)—methane emissions from landfills, as well as nitrous oxide and methane from agricultural waste combustion and to achieve improved waste management. (3).

The National Policy on Electronics (NPE) 2019 envisions to position India as a global hub for Electronics System Design and Manufacturing (ESDM) by encouraging and driving capabilities in the country for developing core components through make in India campaigns, including manufacturing of chipsets. This can give the country the status of fast-growing manufacturer of consumer electronics and creating an enabling environment for the industry to compete globally-Ministry of Electronics & Information Technology (MeitY) 2019. (20)

The current modes of production, consumption and waste-generation linked to different products are responsible for pollution and for around 40% of global greenhouse gas emissions (EU 2020) (23).

Data Analysis

1.1 The importance of circular economy model

Meaning of Circular economy

A circular economy is one, which strives for the longest possible use of products and raw materials till the last stage of its life. In practical terms, this means avoiding waste through reuse or further use means recycling and reuse. If reuse is not possible, they are broken down into their starting materials, i.e., raw materials and then follow the process of recycling. In circular economy reuse the products maximum till the end of its life before recycling. In a linear economy finite resource like fossil fuels used to make products that are then simply thrown away and often have negative effects on the environment or human health or both.

In a recycling economy, the aim is to steadily increase the proportion of secondary raw materials for production. Obtaining secondary raw materials from waste should, therefore, not be seen as a disposal problem, but as part of the raw material supply. The more secondary raw materials are obtained from waste , the more will be the replacement of primary raw

materials in industrial production to avoid the scarcity of raw materials. By using secondary raw materials, considerable amounts of climate-damaging carbon dioxide can be avoided.

A transition towards circular economy will serve more raw materials to reduce dependency on virgin materials and enhance resource productivity. The recovery period of Indian economy from COVID-19 and self-reliance or Atmanirbhar Bharat policy becomes very crucial to the authorities to address. These challenges become easy to overcome through circular economy sustainable growth models. The Indian recovery strategies from COVID-19 need to be sustainable to promote conditions to rebuild for people, environment, and economy. This necessitates increased investment in skills, sectors, processes, products, business models, digitalization and technologies. In this regard, The Ministry of Electronics & Information Technology MeitY launched a 'Product Linked Incentive Scheme (PLI) to boost large scale financial incentives in domestic manufacturing of electronic components and semiconductor packaging.

To understand the need of circular economy the review of growth rate of domestic electronic goods manufacturing sector is necessary. The production of domestic electronic goods in India increased by 187 percent from Rs 1,90,366 crore in 2014-15 to an estimated Rs 5,46,550 crore in 2019-20, with a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of about 24 percent, according to the MeitY's annual report 2019-20 (15). Globally, by 2050, the rate of consumption of resources would be three times higher than the rate at which earth can replenish. For instance, the manufacturing of a ton of laptops, potentially leads to 10 tonnes of CO₂ are emitted. When the carbon dioxide released over a device's lifetime is considered, monitoring of production stage is the most crucial which makes resource efficient production and use of recycled raw materials as inputs at the manufacturing stage.

In 2015, the United Nations General Assembly set up the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) for achieving a better and more sustainable future for all by the year 2030. India is also a signatory to the SDG goals. Some of the SDG's goals are: Responsible Consumption and Production, Sustainable Cities, Communities and Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure are meant for promoting the circular economy. Eventually a large number of businesses, including many electronic manufacturers like Dell, Samsung and HP etc. have announced their specific response plan and strategies for aligning with specific SDGs. Electronic and Electrical Equipment's (EEE) manufacturing sector also dependent on high material consumption and uses metals like Iron, Copper, Silver, Gold, Aluminum, manganese, Chromium and Zinc along with many rare earth elements. Electronic and Electrical waste, collection and management of which remains a key challenge, is one of the rich sources of secondary raw materials and can contribute towards resource security and environmental sustainability. This necessitates the shift to a more circular approach for the sector in a comprehensive manner. Electronics waste (e-waste) is a global challenge and India is also facing the problem due to rapid use and fast disposal of the electronic gadgets by the people and lack of safe disposal facilities available in the country. According to the Global E-waste Monitor 2020, the world generated a striking 53.6 Mt of e-waste, an average of 7.3 kg per capita in 2019 (26). The growing amount of e-waste is directly linked to higher consumption

rates of EEE globally, short product life-cycles, rapid technological advancement and few repair options.

As per the statistics, Asia generated the highest quantity of e-waste in 2019 at 24.9 Mt, followed by the Americas (13.1 Mt) and Europe (12 Mt), while Africa and Oceania generated 2.9 Mt and 0.7 Mt, respectively. As per Global E-Waste Monitor 2020 report (26), India generated 3.2 million tonnes of e-waste in 2019, ranking third after China (10.1 million tonnes) and the United States (6.9 million tonnes). India collected just 10 per cent of the electronic waste (e-waste) estimated to have been generated in the country 2018-19 and 3.5 per cent of that generated in 2017-18, said a recent report by the Central Pollution Control Board (India collected just 3% e-waste generated in 2018, 10% in 2019 as per CPCB report (16). There is a significant gap between e-waste generation and collection for recycling in India needs to be addressed properly. India collected just 10 per cent of the electronic waste (e-waste) estimated to have been generated in the country 2018-19 and 3.5 per cent of that generated in 2017-18, said a recent report by the Central Pollution Control Board (16). The figures have taken into account 21 types of electrical and electronic equipment listed in the E-Waste Management Rules 2016, these include chargers, motherboards, headphones, television sets, discarded computer monitors, mobile phones and other appliances. The actual e-waste collection, however, was lower in both the years - 25,325 tonnes in 2017-18 and 78,281 tonnes in 2018-19. Considering all these consequences, in the guidelines, the environment ministry of India had made the producers responsible for collection of end-of-life electronic products as part of the Extended Producer Responsibility, in line with the global best practice.

As per the statement of pollution board, 1,630 producers were opted Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) authorization as on November 26, 2020. Also, 312 dismantlers or recyclers were authorized in the same period with a capacity of processing 782,080.2 tonne of e-waste every year. These units processed 69,413 tonnes of e-waste in 2017-18 and 164,663 tonnes in 2018-19 (33). In September last year, CPCB issued show-cause notices to 186 producers for not meeting collection targets for 2018-19. The pollution control board also pulled up 292 producers in November last year because their collection centers were either non-complying or non-traceable and threatened to cancel their EPR authorization and take action as per e-waste rules. The report also states that the volume of e-waste that a dismantler or recycler was handling increased over time period but in contrast to this the shed area of these units remained the same.

The rule mandates that dismantlers have a space of 300 square meter for a capacity of 1 tonne of e-waste per day and the same for recyclers is 500 square meters. But it is difficult to follow due to lack of infrastructure.

1.2 The process of introduction of circular business management model in India

To achieve sustainability and resilience and circular economy business model, a critical area that must be addressed in India is the management of municipal, industrial and agricultural wastes in both urban and rural areas. As of 2016, urban areas in India, representing about 377 million people, generated 62 million MT of municipal solid waste

each year. Of this, only about 70% are collected due to insufficient municipal services. About 20% of the collected wastes are treated, and the remaining 50% are disposed in open landfills, without proper treatment or containment. Based on changing consumption patterns and rapid economic growth, urban municipal solid waste generation is projected to reach 165 million MT by 2030 (28).

The journey of sustainable business model in India through circular economy is in the initial stage only. The main hurdles to achieve long-term sustainability is unexpected disturbance such as terrorism, natural calamities and uncertainty. Recently, Covid pandemic and consequent unexpected changes in the life of the people known as VUCCA world also responsible for this slow transition to circular economy. As per direction of NITI Aayog, the MeitY is formulating an action plan for implementation of circular economy principles in electronics products manufacturing sector. Circular economy requires continuous focus on the lifecycle of electronics including stages of raw material acquisition, design, manufacturing/production stage, consumption, to end of life (e-waste) management, and secondary raw materials utilization.

A Systems View of Circular Economy Processes

Below table indicates the process of production in linear economy, reuse economy and circular economy. Circular economy converts used goods in to secondary raw materials after recycling.

Linear Economy	Reuse Economy	Circular Economy
Raw Materials	Raw materials	Raw materials
Production	Production	Production
Use	Use	Use
Non-Recyclable waste	Non-Recyclable waste	Recycling & Use

Circular Business Models can be viable for the economy

According to Andrew Morlet of Ellen MacArthur Foundation, Circular business models will lead to palpable business gains in the near future. For that separate supply-chains and manufacturing set-ups are designed. Circularity is value creation process rather than conservation of resources. Below figure indicates a feasible circular economy model can be applied to Indian economy.

Some key aspects of a Circular Economy: These are some circular economy practices by other firms and companies, which can be implemented easily in India.

Products considered as service:

In which the companies can supply the products with good will to give service till replacement and recycle. For example, Signify (Philips Lighting) in 2015 signed up Schipol Airport to provide light systems as a service to lit the entire building. In this the company ensures the fixtures to last long. Since all the equipment are owned by the company replacement and maintenance costs are slashed and the replacement and recycling will be taken cared by them.

Recycled products as raw materials: Tarkett, a French flooring company adopted circular principle at its core manufacturing strategy. It converts waste in to raw materials by doing research on how to refurbish and reuse the end products. Two-thirds of its raw materials come from recycled materials.

Institutional and Government support: Govt support for this is required to create awareness and implement circularity.

Sustainable method of financing: The banks – ABM Amro, ING, Rabobank – have created circular economy guidelines for other to follow and to evolve the role that finance will play in a circular economy.

Innovative start-ups: The start-up companies can practice CE model government intervention can ensure this while giving consent to them.

Introduction of Landfill Tax: Govts should tax companies and communities for dumping in landfills. It will make the companies to have some built-in solution and avoid the use of valuable urban land, reduce pollution.

1.3 Experience of other economies already introduced CE model

2. Germany

The massive oil crisis faced by Germany during 1970s and the followed economic diversification caused environmental issues led the government to introduce the first waste law enacted in 1972. Further action plan taken by German government developed in to a holistic action plan and environmental programme to protect the environment eventually led to the waste disposal act of 1972. In 1994 as a part of introducing circular economic model, a model of sustainable development was incorporated into the German constitution by adopting the regional planning act and building code in 1998. This was meant to government's commitment to save natural resources, reduce soil sealing, protect the environment conserve biological diversity, and promote sustainable use of resources. Introduced a Systematic Dynamic model with renewable energy and energy-saving regulations, special nature conservation laws, and environmental information law. These laws eventually provided the platform for the shift towards circularity. The German parliament passed the law on complete circular economy in 1996. This law seeks to reduce land for waste disposal based on waste hierarchy of avoidance and closed-loop recycling and also shifts product responsibility to producers. The producers have to design their products to minimize waste, ensure waste recovery, and reuse both in production and use. With the strict implementation, Germany is referred to as the role model of resource recovery.

China

In China, environmentally friendly production and consumption systems and energy savings model has been introduced in all production areas. The 3R principles are achieved by the redesign and rearrangement of city's infrastructure. The macro level planning to achieve circularity includes:

- Development of industry for waste reuse, recycling and safe treatment
- Development of eco-farming by planting-livestock breeding/fishery-food manufacturing model and livestock-methane-fertilizer model and the eco-food and organic food base.
- Environmentally friendly consumption, including public green procurement, green communities, green hotels and restaurants, green buildings, energy saving in governmental offices and households, and certifications for environmentally friendly and energy saving products.

Japan

Japan introduced path to circularity due to lack of landfill space in its rocky topography. It is an island with a high population and large mountainous terrain, explored the concept of circular economy after the global financial crisis. The country is major industrial producer, the move to circularity yielded result only in 1991, after when the law for effective utilization of recyclables was implemented. Japan is the first country to enact CE legislation. The key measures adopted include

reduce oil dependence and high energy consumption industries, improve efficiency of energy utilization, develop knowledge-intensive industries and adjust energy structure. Japan's CE model became a success effective collaboration between consumers and manufacturers. It meant to integrating its people, economy, and social system through optimum utilization of non-renewable resources and strategic changes for renewable resources. Research and development also done to incorporate non-renewable resources in production and created avenues to explore alternative energy and use of renewable resources. The development of high technology and the advancement of technological knowledge has provided a firm foundation for Japan's CE system. The government developed an all-inclusive legal framework for transition of Japan to a CE society, which later became a national living pattern. Important steps taken by the Japanese government to ensure circularity in all sectors include:

- Initiated educational courses on awareness of environmental issues in schools, companies, and communities
- Provision of recycling laboratories in schools to create awareness among the students.
- Provision of enterprises' circular trading markets.
- Provision of incentives to producers and consumers, enhancing public collaboration, and creating customer-friendly stalls for collection of old appliances.
- Provision of waste recycling station in every location.

Manufacturers' roles are use of more recycled materials, production of long-lasting products, and design for repair, reuse, and recycling. Three levels of implementation including enterprises (the main implementing body), industrial parks (waste from one enterprise are transformed into raw material for another), and society (recycling society) were developed. The old materials or products are easily collected; the cost of return and recovery have been added to a product's cost when new and all companies are compelled to recycle their own products strictly. Recycling systems aimed at zero emission were developed, which consist of life cycle assessment system, waste minimization system, resource recycling system, the industry chain of waste recycling and the recycling, transport and trading system of waste. These systems were supported by legislation and regulations.

Recommendations to initiate CE model in India

Awareness programs on e-waste management

Awareness generation play an important part in driving consumer behaviour in India. MeitY has considerable experience due to its awareness raising programmes in the area of e-waste management. Eco-labelling on the products to be used as recycled materials to be done to create the consumer awareness.

Guidelines for Refurbishment, Repairability and Availability of Spare Parts

To improve the competitiveness of circular products and models repairability guidelines with modular designs, availability of spare parts and remanufacturing possibilities to be mentioned on the product profile.

Supporting Consumption Circular and Sustainable Consumption Practices

Awareness and demand for circular consumption must be supported by improved availability of such circular products and services in the market. Such products and services necessitate a larger ecosystem wherein policies and incentives favour the circular products practices. Tax concession and Legal warranty of second-hand and refurbished products will help to increase the quality and value of such products and also helpful to gain consumers' trust.

Product subscription/ lease models

Circular consumption entails a value deriving exercise it includes subscription and rental of product and services along with other innovative models can also help meet the same demand from the people. Consumer's willingness is important in this. It is easy in collecting of e-waste.

Green public procurement (GPP)

Green Public Procurement by the government can be used as strong tool to ensure bulk consumers alignment to the products and circular complying. Proper research and development and strategic approach is needed to implement GPP. The scope of start-ups, budding innovators, NGOs can easily enhance with the introduction of CE in India.

Findings

After conducting a comprehensive study on this topic by verifying various websites, government regulations research articles, practice followed by other countries the researcher identified these aspects which require further effective focus to implement circular economy business model in India. It can save energy, cost, land use and pave the way to attain optimum sustainable economic development in this Vucca world. These are the findings of the research.

- Identification of standard bench mark and targets based on the type of product, purely based on environmental performance with the support of the producers.
- Introduction of award schemes/incentives for motivating the producers to initiate CE model.
- Provision of incentives /tax concessions to those manufacturers whose products reach the benchmark within a stipulated time-period.
- Engage informal sector also as stakeholder in E-waste Rules and monitor their performance with the help of local government to ensure integrated sustainable business development.

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- Effective Management and Monitoring of Hazardous Waste
 - Increase Incentives for Investment in Recycling Technologies and Facilities
 - Provision of technical support to design electronics for longevity and recyclability.
 - Ensure the availability and sourcing of recycled raw materials to substitute the demand for new raw materials.
 - Encourage the consumers to use and reuse by introducing incentives and awareness campaign to throw light on environmental, health, and safety impacts of e-waste.
 - Set Up effective collection centers and high-standard recycling plant for e-waste.
 - Effective monitoring of the stages of transition to a Circular Economy for Electronics.

Conclusion

In this research paper based the conceptual understanding of micro and macro levels of operational issues to implement CE business model, the researcher tried to include pros and cons of excessive growth of electronic manufacturing sector. This study also discusses about the scope to reduce process waste to the manufacturers and how to attain sustainability through CE business model with the support of the authorities. It also unveils the possibility of use of secondary raw materials to increase production and reduce landfill to avoid heavy pressure on land.

Scope for further research

This research is based on secondary data and the current literature available. Therefore, in future research development one can integrate CE model and Industry 4.0 to have better insight in this topic. By incorporating primary data collected from consumers and producers about the possibility of introducing CE business model the study can be elaborated. Especially, the unexpected dynamic changes we have noticed in the society during Covid pandemic (VUCCA world) to integrate resources and capabilities across regions to ensure public health study on the CE model can be served as a support system to face this uncertainty. A detailed comparative analysis can be conducted on this to identify the issues India is facing to implement CE model based on the experience of Japan, Germany and China.

References

1. Schumacher, K., & Green, M. L. (2021). Circular Economy in the High-Tech World Workshop Report. NIST Special Publication, 1500, 204..
2. Lahti, T., Wincent, J., & Parida, V. (2018). A definition and theoretical review of the circular economy, value creation, and sustainable business models: where are we now and where should research move in the future?. *Sustainability*, 10(8), 2799.
3. Fiksel, J., Sanjay, P., & Raman, K. (2021). Steps toward a resilient circular economy in India. *Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy*, 23(1), 203-218.
4. Fatimah, Y. A., Govindan, K., Murniningsih, R., & Setiawan, A. (2020). Industry 4.0 based sustainable circular economy approach for smart waste management system to achieve sustainable development goals: A case study of Indonesia. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 269, 122263.

5. Kumar, V., Sezersan, I., Garza-Reyes, J. A., Gonzalez, E. D., & Moh'd Anwer, A. S. (2019). Circular economy in the manufacturing sector: benefits, opportunities and barriers. *Management Decision*.
 6. Islam, M. T., Huda, N., Baumber, A., Shumon, R., Zaman, A., Ali, F., ... & Sahajwalla, V. (2021). A global review of consumer behavior towards e-waste and implications for the circular economy. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 316, 128297.
 7. Dantas, T. E., De-Souza, E. D., Destro, I. R., Hammes, G., Rodriguez, C. M. T., & Soares, S. R. (2021). How the combination of Circular Economy and Industry 4.0 can contribute towards achieving the Sustainable Development Goals. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 26, 213-227.
 8. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0959652615018442#preview-section-introduction>
 9. https://www.meity.gov.in/writereaddata/files/Circular_Economy_EEE-Meity-May2021-ver7.pdf. (n.d.).
 10. https://ficcices.in/pdf/FICCI-Accenture_Circular%20Economy%20Report_OptVer.pdf. (n.d.).
 11. <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1657534/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
 12. https://tsapps.nist.gov/publication/get_pdf.cfm?pub_id=933390. (n.d.).
 13. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/09537287.2022.2063198?cookieSet=1>. (n.d.).
 14. <https://www.federalreserve.gov/releases/g17/current/default.htm>
 15. https://www.meity.gov.in/writereaddata/files/EWaste_Sep11_892011.pdf. (n.d.)
 16. <https://www.downtoearth.org.in/news/waste/india-collected-just-3-e-waste-generated-in-2018-10-in-2019-cpcb-report-75072>. (n.d.).
 17. https://www.wto.org/english/tratop_e/tessd_e/wef_18may22.pdf. (n.d.).
 18. O'Connor, M. P., Zimmerman, J. B., Anastas, P. T., & Plata, D. L. (2016). A strategy for material supply chain sustainability: enabling a circular economy in the electronics industry through green engineering. (n.d.).
 19. <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/14/6/3268>. (n.d.). <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/14/6/3268>.
 20. https://www.meity.gov.in/writereaddata/files/Circular_Economy_EEE-Meity-May2021-ver7.pdf. (n.d.).
 21. Chang, P. Y., Fiksel, G., Hohenberger, M., Knauer, J. P., Betti, R., Marshall, F. J., ... & Petrasso, R. D. (2011). Fusion yield enhancement in magnetized laser-driven implosions. *Physical review letters*, 107(3), 035006.
 22. <https://cpcb.nic.in/e-waste-recyclers-dismantler/>. (n.d.).
 23. <https://www.sdgindex.org/reports/europe-sustainable-development-report-2020/>. (n.d.).
 24. <https://www.bls.gov/cex/>. (n.d.).
 25. <https://www.infinumgrowth.com/circular-business-models/circular-economy/>. (n.d.).
 26. <https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-D/Environment/Pages/Spotlight/Global-Ewaste-Monitor-2020.aspx>. (n.d.).
 27. <https://cpcb.nic.in/openpdf.php?id=UmVwb3J0RmlsZXNvMTQwM18xNjU1MzU0NzkyX21lZGlhcGhvdG8xNjQ3MS5wZGY=>. (n.d.).
 28. <http://www.indiaenvironmentportal.org.in/>. (n.d.).
 29. <https://ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/circular-examples/a-model-offering-multiple-benefits-for-multiple-electronic-products>. (n.d.).
 30. https://www.compasseducation.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/Splosh_EMF.pdf. (n.d.).
 31. <https://ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/circular-examples/cradle-to-cradle-design-of-carpets>. (n.d.).
 32. <https://www.bls.gov/cex/csreport.htm>. (n.d.).
 33. <https://pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=1842627>. (n.d.).
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